

International court actions in practise: problems of the Polish judiciary

The courts of all countries daily apply the norms of international law in conducting cases and other judicial activities. Courts apply, depending on the need, the norms of public international law and private international law, as well as mixed provisions of international law, such as European Union law. The greatest scope of using international law occurs in the field of the judicial function (judgement), where increasingly often, judges issue judgments solely on the basis of acts of international law, or in conjunction with national law (foreign domestic law or implemented international law).¹

In addition, courts perform other international, non-judicial activities. We can call them international auxiliary court actions. They include all the activities of courts that do not concern the performance of the judicial function and administrative activities of the court as an organization. In Polish practise of law, it has been accepted that these are court actions such as delivering correspondence abroad, providing legal assistance abroad, taking evidence abroad, performing translations, document authentication, execution of court judgments abroad, execution of a foreign judgment and other activities defined by international law. The Polish court may perform auxiliary activities at the request of another country (as the requested court) or request similar procedures to be carried out abroad (as the requesting court). In certain cases, court actions may also apply to other foreign entities (e. g. the police, court bailiffs, social welfare, consuls, post offices). In reality, international auxiliary activities play a dominant role in court proceedings; sometimes more important than issuing a judgment. Hence, activities supporting the judging function should be given the same high rank.²

¹ Joe McIntyre, 'Introduction to the Judicial Function', in *The Judicial Function: Fundamental Principles of Contemporary Judging*, ed. Joe McIntyre (Singapore: Springer, 2019), 23–31, doi:10.1007/978-981-32-9115-7_2; Joe McIntyre, 'The Development of Principles of Contemporary Judging', in *The Judicial Function: Fundamental Principles of Contemporary Judging*, ed. Joe McIntyre (Singapore: Springer, 2019), 3–19, doi:10.1007/978-981-32-9115-7_1; Katja S. Ziegler, 'The Relationship between EU Law and International Law', SSRN Scholarly Paper (Rochester, NY: Social Science Research Network, 22 January 2015), 3–17, <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=2554069>; Violeta Moreno-Lax and Paul Gragl, 'Introduction: Beyond Monism, Dualism, Pluralism: The Quest for a (Fully-Fledged) Theoretical Framework: Co-Implication, Embeddedness, and Interdependency between Public International Law and EU Law', *Yearbook of European Law* 35, no. 1 (1 December 2016): 455–470, doi:10.1093/yel/yew016.

² 'Rozporządzenie Ministra Sprawiedliwości z Dnia 28 Stycznia 2002 r. w Sprawie Szczegółowych Czynności Sądów w Sprawach z Zakresu Międzynarodowego Postępowania Cywilnego Oraz Karnego w Stosunkach Międzynarodowych', Pub. L. No. Dz. U. z 2014 r. poz. 1657 z późn. zm.) (n.d.); Sławomir R Buczma and Józef Gemra, *Metodyka pracy w sprawach karnych ze stosunków międzynarodowych* (Warszawa; Kraków: Wydawnictwo C. H. Beck; Krajowa Szkoła Sądownictwa i Prokuratury, 2013), 4–145, <https://www.kSSIP.gov.pl/kSSIP/sites/default/files/068fb43699bf48acc340057c76333f16.pdf>; Andrzej Wróbel,

The complexity of conducting international activities in courts is increasing; this creates numerous problems, errors and omissions when international law is applied in exercising the judging function. In addition, the number of practical problems is also growing as part of the auxiliary activities in international relations. Unfortunately, the number of problems is quite large and virtually constant. Problems are mainly noticed by court staff other than judges; however, they usually affect the parties to the proceedings and their attorneys. Generally lawyers and solicitors know them well but deny them. It is logical to ask Polish jurists how they perceive the courts' performance of judicial and auxiliary functions within international legal relations. Lawyers in particular, from an external perspective, observe problems in the courts most objectively.³

Based on the preliminary analysis of the literature and reports we are able to state general hypotheses. Polish courts regularly use acts of international law as part of their judicial function. However, the number of problems related to their application by judges is steadily increasing. Polish courts also carry out more and more international auxiliary activities, with growing problems. Only some of the international procedures are used and noticed by the parties' attorneys, while others are a "dead letter of the law" or are used very rarely. Numerous problems regarding these auxiliary activities cause low efficiency in handling cases with international elements. The lack of reforms to international activities in the field of judicial functions and auxiliary activities will soon result in the regression of Polish courts, and block the Polish judiciary's international cooperation with other European Union countries.

Therefore, in this study we would like confirm these hypotheses mentioned above. Their testing should be based on empirical research conducted with independent, external observers. Hence, Polish advocates and legal advisers are interviewed, in order to define, deepen and explain the subject of Polish court problems related to performing the judicial function and auxiliary activities in the field of international court procedures.

ed., *Stosowanie prawa Unii Europejskiej przez sądy*, vol. 1 (Warszawa: Wolters Kluwer, 2010), 384–435, 468–555.

³ Grzegorz Chmiel, 'Obrót zagraniczny w praktyce', 10 May 2021, <https://forumfws.eu/obr%C3%B3t-zagraniczny-materia%C5%82y-szkoleniowe-g.-chmiel.pdf>; 'Forum Współpracy Sędziów', *FWS*, accessed 15 May 2021, <https://forumfws.eu/inicjatywy-lokalne/sedziowie-lodzcy/>; Rafał Skibicki, 'Międzynarodowe Postępowanie Cywilne' (Wrocław, 10 February 2021), <https://prawo.uni.wroc.pl/sites/default/files/students-resources/Zaj%C4%99cia%20nr%2010%20-%20MPC.pdf>.

Methodology

The results of this research are a component of a larger study on the internationalization of the Polish justice and legal services, which was carried out from 7 August 2017 to 22 January 2019, and supplemented in the period from November 2020 to March 2021. The study was performed using several research methods. Thanks to their triangulation, the obtained results were mutually checked, supplemented and extended. The following methods were used for this component:

1. Semi-structured in-depth interviews (SSI) with a group of 43 advocates (*adwokat*) and legal advisers (*radca prawny*) - representatives of councils of district bar associations (*Okręgowa Rada Adwokacka, ORA*) and councils of district chambers of legal advisers (*rada Okręgowej Izby Radców Prawnych, OIRP*). Results were collected and interpreted in a meaning-oriented manner. Each bar association was represented by at least one participant. The interviews were conducted in person and recorded; then transcribed, coded, categorized and translated into English. The Skrybot and Atlas.ti software were used. The study is strictly qualitative.⁴
2. Examination of non-reactive materials: analysis of international legal acts conducted by the legal functional method; literature content analysis⁵.

Detailed methodological information is available in the report prepared for the entire study. Source data are stored for further use.⁶

The study analyses only those problems, related to the functioning of courts in international relations, that are empirically known by the respondents in reality. Due to the fact

⁴ Joanne Horton, Richard Macve, and Geert Struyven, 'Qualitative Research: Experiences in Using Semi-Structured Interviews', in *The Real Life Guide to Accounting Research*, ed. Christopher Humphrey and Bill Lee (Oxford: Elsevier, 2004), 339–57, doi:10.1016/B978-008043972-3/50022-0; Steinar Kvale, *Prowadzenie wywiadów*, trans. Agata Dziuban, Niezbędnik Badacza (Warszawa: Wydawnictwo Naukowe PWN, 2012), 170–178, <http://emp0pwn0storage0prod.blob.core.windows.net/kipwnaddons/65438.pdf>; Michele J. McIntosh and Janice M. Morse, 'Situating and Constructing Diversity in Semi-Structured Interviews', *Global Qualitative Nursing Research*, no. 2 (1 January 2015): 1–12, doi:10.1177/2333393615597674; Małgorzata Nicpoń and Radosław Marzęcki, 'Pogłębiony wywiad indywidualny w badaniach politologicznych', in *Przeszłość, teraźniejszość, przyszłość: problemy badawcze młodych politologów* (Kraków: Libron, 2010), 246–51, <http://przemek.wammoda.com/polis/ksmp/book/IIKSMPmarzecki.pdf>; Ilona Przybyłowska, 'Wywiad swobodny ze standaryzowaną listą poszukiwanych informacji i możliwości jego zastosowania w badaniach socjologicznych', *Przegląd Socjologiczny*, no. 30 (1978): 62–64; Sandy Q Qu and John Dumay, 'The Qualitative Research Interview', *Qualitative Research in Accounting & Management* 8, no. 3 (2011): 238–61; 'SkryBot', *Skrybot*, 2021, <https://skrybot.pl>; 'ATLAS.ti', *ATLAS.ti*, 2021, <https://atlasti.com/>.

⁵ Earl R Babbie, *Podstawy Badań Społecznych*, trans. Witold Betkiewicz (Warszawa: Wydawnictwo Naukowe PWN, 2008), 342–60; Chava Frankfort-Nachmias and David Nachmias, *Metody Badawcze w Naukach Społecznych* (Poznań: Zysk i S-ka, 2001); Dawid Kędzierski, 'Metodologia i Paradygmat Polskich Szczegółowych Nauk Prawnych', *Transformacje Prawa Prywatnego*, no. 3 (29 September 2018): 34–46.

⁶ Stanisław Lipiec, 'Świadczenie Międzynarodowych Usług Prawniczych. Studium Socjologiczno-Prawne Polskich Prawników, Rozprawa Doktorska' (rozprawa doktorska, 2020).

that the research is based on the personal experience of lawyers, it is not possible to notice problems in the areas existing only theoretically in legal acts.

The research report includes the following terms: legal transactions with foreign countries, international elements, foreign affairs, international affairs, and international cooperation, or “Oz” or “Kop”. The latter is related to cases that are marked as involving international relations in court documentation (“Oz” - civil cases list, “Kop” - criminal cases list).⁷ We will treat the indicated terms as synonyms defining the entirety of international judicial activities undertaken as part of the judicial function, as well as auxiliary activities.

The research has a sociological dimension and concerns a broad paradigm of legal sociology and legal anthropology. The research works of Richard Abel and Adam Podgórecki greatly influenced its construction and implementation. The general theoretical assumptions were based on the principles of grounded theory as interpreted by Kathy Charmaz. The guide for the interviews was Steiner Kvale. In the case of non-reactive research (*content analysis*), the scientific activity of Bernard Berelson was also important, in the interpretation of Walery Pisarek⁸.

An equal number of legal advisers (*radca prawny*) and advocates (*adwokat*) participated in the research (22 and 21 people, respectively), evenly distributed throughout the country and representing all bar associations in Poland and the supreme bodies (*Naczelna Rada Adwokacka*, *NRA* and *Krajowa Rada Radców Prawnych*, *KRRP*).⁹ The population is dominated by men (59% to 41%), which is reflected in the research sample. The most active group of lawyers in Poland are people aged 30 to 50, which is also reflected in the research sample.¹⁰ It was noted that all the studied lawyers speak at least one foreign language. English is the dominant language (62%), followed by Russian (29% of responses).¹¹

⁷ §385, §456 ‘Zarządzenie Ministra Sprawiedliwości z Dnia 19 Czerwca 2019 r. w Sprawie Organizacji i Zakresu Działania Sekretariatów Sądowych Oraz Innych Działów Administracji Sądowej’, Pub. L. No. Dz. U. M. S. z 2019 r, poz. 138 (2019), <https://www.infor.pl/akt-prawny/U06.2019.043.0000138,zarzadzenie-ministra-sprawiedliwosci-w-sprawie-organizacji-i-zakresu-dzialania-sekretariatow-sadowych-oraz-innych-dzialow-administracji-sadowej.html>.

⁸ Bernard Berelson, *Content Analysis in Communication Research* (New York: Hafner, 1971); Walery Pisarek, *Analiza Zawartości Prasy* (Kraków: Ośrodek Badań Prasoznawczych, 1983).

⁹ ‘Krajowa Izba Radców Prawnych’, *Krajowa Izba Radców Prawnych*, 2021, <http://kirp.pl>; ‘Naczelna Rada Adwokacka’, 2021, <http://www.nra.pl>.

¹⁰ Katarzyna Borowska, ‘Coraz więcej kobiet jest adwokatami’, *Rzeczpospolita*, no. 01.08.2012, accessed 12 May 2021, <https://www.rp.pl/artykul/920818-Coraz-wiecej-kobiet-jest-adwokatami.html>; Maria Stypułkowska, ‘Trudna droga kobiet do wykonywania zawodów prawniczych’, *Palestra* 38, no. 9–10 (1994): 139–49.

¹¹ Joanna Cholewa, ‘Jak język polski i francuski odzwierciedla wzajemne postrzeganie Polaków i Francuzów?’, in *Anglosasi, Francuzi i Polacy: wzajemny wizerunek dawniej i dziś*, ed. Piotr Guzowski and Małgorzata Kamecka (Białystok: Wydawnictwo Uniwersytetu w Białymstoku, 2005), 313–23,

Judgment function, major weaknesses

The international activity of courts, despite many changes, is usually perceived from the perspective of its problems and imperfections, in the performance of both judging functions and auxiliary activities. Other international activities of courts are usually perceived positively; these include cooperation with other courts, the operation of EU judicial information points, social cooperation, and the activity of international cooperation coordinators.¹² Cases related to the performance of foreign activities face many problems, related to the low experience of judiciary employees and the lack of competence in this area; a small number of cases or other opportunities for foreign contacts; as well as the lack of institutional support.¹³

Figure 1 The main problems of cases with international elements

https://repozytorium.uwb.edu.pl/jspui/bitstream/11320/4650/1/Joanna_Cholewa_Jak_jezyk_polski_i_francuski_odzwierciedla_wzajemne_postrzeganie_Polakow_i_Francuzow.pdf; Katarzyna Kloc, 'Język obcy a praca w zawodzie prawnika', *Goldenline.pl*, 2020, https://www.goldenline.pl/grupy/Przedsiębiorcy_biznesmeni/prawo/jezyk-obcy-a-praca-w-zawodzie-prawnika,1770622/; Ilona Wysmułek and Olena Oleksiyenko, *Strukturalne zróżnicowanie znajomości języków obcych: wybrane wyniki Polskiego Badania Panelowego POLPAN 1988-2013* (Warszawa: Zespół Porównawczych Analiz Nierówności Społecznych, Instytut Filozofii i Socjologii Polskiej Akademii Nauk, 2015), http://polpan.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/05/POLPAN_raport_Znajomosc-jezykow.pdf.

¹² Buczman and Gemra, *Metodyka pracy w sprawach karnych ze stosunków międzynarodowych*, 107–32; art. 16b - art. 16d 'Ustawa z Dnia 27 Lipca 2001 r. Prawo o Urzędzie Sądów Powszechnych', Pub. L. No. Dz. U. z 2020 r. poz. 2072 (n.d.); 'European Judicial Network (EJN)', accessed 1 November 2020, https://www.ejn-crimjust.europa.eu/ejn/EJN_Home.aspx.

¹³ Chmiel, 'Obrót zagraniczny w praktyce'; 'Forum Współpracy Sędziów'.

Representatives of legal advisers and advocates participating in the survey are knowledgeable about matters relating to international cases of Polish courts. Because they remain outside the judicial apparatus, they mainly notice those elements of foreign life of the courts in which they represent the parties. They also divide the court problems in Oz cases into those concerning the functions of the judging and the auxiliary activities.

Commonly mentioned are problems with the judging function and its exercise by judges. Polish lawyers emphasize that most judges and other court employees are factually unprepared to handle cases with foreign elements. They blame this on the defective system of legal education at universities, the lack of international topics covered during judicial apprenticeship, and the failure to organize courses and training in cross-border cases during the continuing education of judges and other court employees.¹⁴ We note that only judges can self-improve in the practice of the Oz and Kop affairs; but due to the lack of time and the complexity of such cases, judges prefer to give up self-study. Other court employees try to compensate for the emerging competence problems among arbitrators; hence, they are also the main support for lawyers and judges. However, the training system does not enable the improvement of their competences in foreign affairs, which shows a need for increased self-education.¹⁵

Employees' support of judges in Oz cases is inherently limited, as only the latter are called to exercise the judiciary function. This often leads to situations in which judges cannot deal with foreign elements in the simplest cases, which can be seen at hearings and in other contacts between lawyers and judges. Some judges notice their competence shortcomings and try to introduce national procedures in place of cross-border procedures; often wrongly. There is a small group of judges who specialize in international matters; however, their number does not exceed 20 in all Polish courts.¹⁶ International elements are present in many cases conducted by all judges. Such a small group does not alleviate the general competence problems of judges and other court employees in foreign matters.

Polish judges' and other court employees' lack of knowledge in this field is particularly visible when there is a need to refer to acts of international law, jurisprudence of international tribunals, and to conduct cases based on the law of foreign countries. Polish

¹⁴ Lipiec, 'Świadczenie Międzynarodowych Usług Prawniczych. Studium Socjologiczno-Prawne Polskich Prawników, Rozprawa Doktorska', 345–67, 756–811.

¹⁵ 'Nasze Szkolenia Ustawiczne', *Krajowa Szkoła Sądownictwa i Prokuratury*, accessed 15 May 2021, https://ekSSIP.kSSIP.gov.pl/local/guest_pages/our-courses.php; 'Aplikacja sędziowska', *Krajowa Szkoła Sądownictwa i Prokuratury*, accessed 15 May 2021, [/aplikacje/programy-aplikacji/aplikacja-sedziowska](https://ekSSIP.kSSIP.gov.pl/aplikacje/programy-aplikacji/aplikacja-sedziowska).

¹⁶ 'Forum Współpracy Sędziów'; Bogna Kociołowicz-Wiśniewska and Bartosz Pilitowski, *Ocena polskiego sądownictwa w świetle badań* (Warszawa: Fundacja Court Watch Polska, 2017), 15–24, <https://courtwatch.pl/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/Raport-Fundacji-Court-Watch-Polska-Ocena-polskich-s%C4%85d%C3%B3w-w-%C5%9Bwielu-bada%C5%84-maj-2017.pdf>.

attorneys emphasize that most judges very rarely refer to acts of international law and the case law of the European Court of Human Rights or the Court of Justice of the European Union. In the interviewees' opinion, this is noticeable during hearings and in the justifications of judgments, and applies to criminal law, civil law and other branches. Even when using the instruments of international law already introduced into the domestic legal order, Polish courts avoid referring directly to EU directives and regulations or treaties. Instead, they derive legal norms only from domestic law, even when they should be derived from acts of international law.¹⁷ Legal specialists from Torun, Bydgoszcz and Radom see this problem in this way:

Polish judges think that this does not concern them, and that it concerns [CJEU case law - St. L.]. For example, I have a big problem with explaining that it concerns them. Judges do not know the case law because there is a language barrier. And if they do, they only refer to judgments that have already been translated into Polish. [Otherwise] they are unable to read it and understand it. Even in Warsaw.

For a long time, we could refer to the constitution and the jurisprudence of tribunals. The judges just [disregarded - St. L.]. The lawyer might have complained about this. They didn't care. But more and more they pay attention to it, and I think now because the constitution has been rediscovered and it concerns them and the judiciary, they are starting to pay more and more attention to it. I remember how, five or six years ago, an elderly attorney very often referred to the judgments of the tribunals, there were even laughs and comments about him. Poland is like this... But it is changing for the better. I don't know if the judges have any training in this area. Anyway, here in the Bar Association we did a training with judges from Gdansk. [...] But this [training - St. L.] did not translate into any complaints, they do not want it; if he gets something ex officio that says he has to write a complaint, it's unacceptable!

It has never happened to me before the court in Radom that the courts referred to [the judgments of the CJEU - St. L.]. However, despite the large number of hearings before the courts of appeal – Warsaw, Lublin, recently I had Poznan, Bialystok – it happened once to me that the thesis of the judgment of the European court was quoted at the hearing. Once. Generally, Polish courts are based on Polish jurisprudence. At least in the things I do. I don't know about the others. However, when it comes to the justification of judgments of the courts of appeal or the supreme court, it happened once in my cases that the CJEU judgment was quoted in the justification. It is not a dominant thing.

¹⁷ 'European Court of Human Rights', accessed 16 January 2020, <https://www.echr.coe.int/Pages/home.aspx?p=home>; 'Court of Justice of the European Union', accessed 15 May 2021, https://curia.europa.eu/jcms/jcms/j_6/en/; Wróbel, *Stosowanie prawa Unii Europejskiej przez sądy*, 1:918–1014; Maciej Szpunar, 'Wybrane problemy stosowania prawa Unii Europejskiej przed sądami państw członkowskich', *Palestra*, no. 5 (2020), <https://palestra.pl/pl/czasopismo/wydanie/5-2020/artykul/wybrane-problemy-stosowania-prawa-unii-europejskiej-przed-sadami-panstw-czlonkowskich>.

Polish judges almost never refer questions for a preliminary ruling to international courts. Hence, the fact of sending the inquiry is a very surprising. Moreover, they themselves do not undertake a conscious application of international law and its interpretation. If a judge is ready to send a legal question to an international court, it is usually the person concerned, i.e. the attorney, who prepares the application, and the court only checks it and passes it on.¹⁸ A lawyer from Warsaw emphasizes this situation clearly:

However, there are few criminal cases, because the courts do not want to refer legal questions to tribunals. The criminal courts in Poland have nothing to do with the preliminary questions.

Some lawyers emphasize situations in which courts had to apply foreign law, such as Swiss or Chinese law, in practice. The results were highly unsatisfactory and tended to do more harm than good. The judges and court staff were completely unprepared and surprised by the necessity. At that time, they tried to apply Polish law instead of foreign law, despite the fact that such an obligation resulted from the provisions of law and contractual regulations. Probably, along with Poland's deeper integration with other countries, such obligations will appear more often¹⁹. The situation in Czestochowa provides an example:

We argued for a long time, because this case was dependent on the choice of law and it just ended with the court ruling on the basis of Chinese law. The Polish court ruled on the basis of Chinese law! In both cases – Switzerland and China – I believe that the court failed to deal with it. In the first case, it ended with the fact that the parties in Switzerland came to an agreement and it did not have any further result.

Polish lawyers also notice problems with the choice of jurisdiction; this is particularly important in family matters, when the litigants are located in different countries, and sometimes also occurs in civil cases. Lawyers often get the impression that many judges are unable to determine the substantive and local jurisdiction and applicable law when there are doubts about domestic and foreign jurisdiction. In such situations, most often they try to apply national

¹⁸ Bartosz Czekala and Bogusław Kromołowski, 'Pytania prejudycjalne do Trybunału Sprawiedliwości Unii Europejskiej w polskim postępowaniu karnym', *Gubernaculum et Administratio* 2015, no. 1 (11) (2015): 23–25; Jacek Barcik, 'Pytania Prejudycjalne Polskich Sądów', *Iustitia*, no. 3 (2013): 1–4; Jacek Sadomski, 'Pytania prejudycjalne polskich sądów powszechnych', *Prawo w Działaniu*, no. 20 (2014): 34–90.

¹⁹ Marta Cichomska, 'Wybór prawa w postępowaniu cywilnym' (rozprawa doktorska, Uniwersytet Warszawski, 2015), 258–385, <https://depotuw.ceon.pl/handle/item/1212>.

jurisdiction in all aspects, especially regarding the best interests of the child. Alternatively, they refer the cases to the appropriate Regional Court of Warsaw (*Sąd Rejonowy dla Miasta Stołecznego Warszawy*) or the District Court of Warsaw (*Sąd Okręgowy w Warszawie*) by default.²⁰ This problem is related to the judges' lack of knowledge of private international law and other acts of international law that indicate the rules of jurisdiction.²¹ As a consequence, foreign parties are often severely discriminated against, due to the necessity to conduct cases in Poland. Nevertheless, Polish parties benefit from such incompetence of judges, which enables them to conduct foreign affairs in Polish courts.

Nevertheless, lawyers note that judges and court employees treat foreign lawyers appearing in Polish courts with a great deal of understanding.²² During hearings, judges openly support foreign lawyers and provide instructions and comments. Also, imperfectly prepared pleadings are accepted and understood. Furthermore, the interviewees do not notice that foreign parties or their representatives are discriminated against in the courts. In their opinion, there are no symptoms of judicial discrimination against citizens of other countries, on either the legal or moral level. This situation is now considered a normal phenomenon, although there have reportedly been various signs of judicial intolerance towards foreigners in the past.

Auxiliary actions, basic problems

Courts are huge institutions that perform other tasks in addition to their judging function. Polish advocates and legal advisers very often emphasize that auxiliary activities in international cases are performed incorrectly, mainly due to the huge inflation of cases and insufficient human resources. Moreover, court clerks, court recorders and assistant judges do not specialize in Oz and Kop cases; they do whatever the judges order. This results in a rush of matters and a waste of competences, as well as employees' ability and energy. Additionally, there is a lack of suitable system and IT tools, organizational resources, and time for auxiliary activities in international affairs. Foreign duties are taken on when absolutely necessary, at the last minute. There is also a lack of permanent cooperation between judges, employees and the outside world, in cases with foreign elements; as well as insufficient organization of departments, or specialists

²⁰ 'Sąd Rejonowy Dla m.St. Warszawy w Warszawie', accessed 15 May 2021, <http://warszawa.sr.gov.pl/>; 'Sąd Okręgowy w Warszawie', accessed 15 May 2021, <https://bip.warszawa.so.gov.pl/>.

²¹ Wróbel, *Stosowanie prawa Unii Europejskiej przez sądy*, 1:468–504; Jacek Gołaczyński et al., *Kolizyjne i procesowe aspekty prawa rodzinnego* (Warszawa: Wydawnictwo C H. Beck, 2019).

²² Stanisław Rymar, 'Świadczenie stałej pomocy prawnej w Polsce przez zagranicznych prawników', *Palestra*, no. 7–8 (2002): 7–11; Lipiec, 'Świadczenie Międzynarodowych Usług Prawniczych. Studium Socjologiczno-Prawne Polskich Prawników, Rozprawa Doktorska', 567–93.

for foreign affairs, in most Polish courts.²³ In the opinion of Polish legal specialists, auxiliary judicial activity in foreign matters is chaotic, accidental, and pushed to the background in the daily activities of courts.

Figure 2 Problems of foreign correspondence delivery

The most serious problems of Polish courts in the field of auxiliary activities are matters of delivering correspondence abroad and collecting evidence abroad. Every Polish lawyer, judge and court employee notices that these two disciplines are the biggest problem in handling cases with foreign elements. The service of court correspondence is one of the most important elements of the Polish civil and criminal procedure, as well as in many other countries. However, there is a fundamental problem: the delivery systems differ from country to country. Failure to deliver or poor performance can have various effects. Therefore, cross-border delivery is of particular importance and is especially complicated. Despite the existence of European and supra-European acts of international law regulating the issue of service, their enforcement still poses particular problems for courts. Collecting correspondence from foreign courts also causes much trouble for litigants and their attorneys. Importantly, most of the tasks related to sending and receiving correspondence are performed by court employees, not judges. The number of service operations is sometimes so large that court secretariats are not able to execute them correctly and quickly.²⁴

²³ Krystyna Daniel, 'Kryzys społecznego zaufania do sądów', *Studia Socjologiczne* 2 (185) (2007): 66–80; Kamil Joński, *Efektywność sądownictwa powszechnego - podstawowe problemy* (Warszawa: Instytut Wymiaru Sprawiedliwości, 2016), https://iws.gov.pl/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/IWS_Jo%C5%84ski-K._Efektywno%C5%9B%C4%87-s%C4%85downictwa-powszechnego1.pdf; Bartosz Michalski, 'Pracownicy sądów doszli do ściany. Urzędnicy i asystenci odchodzą, nowych nie widać', *Dziennik. Gazeta Prawna*, 15 May 2019, <https://prawo.gazetaprawna.pl/artykuly/1411938,protest-oczami-pracownikow-sadownictwa.html>.

²⁴ Chmiel, 'Obrót zagraniczny w praktyce'; 'Forum Współpracy Sędziów'; Renata Lewicka, 'Doręczenia zagraniczne w postępowaniu administracyjnym i sądowniczym – problemy praktyczne', *Acta Universitatis Lodzensis. Folia Iuridica*, no. 77 (2016): 155–70, doi:10.18778/0208-6069.77.12; 'Doręczenia Pism Sądowych w Postępowaniu Cywilnym w Obrocie Krajowym' (rozprawa doktorska, Uniwersytet im. Adama Mickiewicza w Poznaniu, 2012), 35–78, https://repozytorium.amu.edu.pl/bitstream/10593/5797/1/Daria_Dasewicz-Buchowska.pdf; Piotr Ryński, 'Skuteczność doręczeń w procesie cywilnym', *Prawo w Działaniu. Sprawy Cywilne*, no. 15 (2013): 55–82; Jan Ciszewski, *Obrót prawny z zagranicą w sprawach cywilnych i karnych* (Warszawa: Wolters Kluwer, 2017).

Polish lawyers also notice other problems related to the delivery of correspondence abroad, or from abroad to Polish courts. A particular issue is the duration of delivery abroad, which can extend the case by about three months. Currently, Polish procedures sanction the minimum duration of cases. Polish lawyers note that when deliveries to non-European countries are required, the period for service may exceed six months. It is virtually impossible to effectively deliver court correspondence to regions such as African countries, the Caucasus countries, Central America, Arab countries, or disputed and unrecognized territories, such as Transnistria and the occupied territories of Ukraine. In such cases, courts repeatedly attempt to effect service through procedures specified in international conventions, EU law, bilateral agreements, service by Polish diplomatic missions or through diplomatic channels; but these are also often ineffective and sometimes prolong the proceedings by years.²⁵ In most cases, there is no solution to this problem, although the courts are trying to achieve legal service in Poland. Thus, they consider that delivering correspondence to Polish addresses is effective, but this is very often incorrect.

Foreign service of correspondence is the greatest problem of Oz (Kop) matters, especially for court employees. Moreover, it is rarely certain that the international delivery package has arrived and caused the appropriate legal effects, as in most countries shipments are not delivered with return confirmation of receipt.²⁶ This situation may even undermine the validity of specific proceedings taking place in Poland. Service in cases of cross-border family law deserves particular attention, given its importance to the welfare of the family and the child. Unfortunately, we observe special delays in delivery; indeed, most often in family-care cases, courts accept fictions of service in the country, instead of correctly delivering abroad.

Polish legal specialists also emphasize specific problems in regional courts (*sądy rejonowe*), related to the delivery of correspondence, caused by employees' low experience in cross-border cases and the limited number of Oz and Kop cases. The situation is much better in district courts (*sądy okręgowe*), although they have variable efficiency in performing foreign activities. Due to the systemic involvement of districts in matters with foreign elements, they put more emphasis on increasing the professionalism of all employees in this area. Appropriate organizational units or judges are also appointed in judicial districts; and even coordinators for international cooperation. Therefore, the district courts' shortcomings in international matters

²⁵ 'Doręczenia Pism Sądowych w Postępowaniu Cywilnym w Obrocie Krajowym', 35–78; Ciszewski, *Obrót prawny z zagranicą w sprawach cywilnych i karnych*.

²⁶ Chmiel, 'Obrót zagraniczny w praktyce'.

have been diminishing recently.²⁷ We hope that this trend will continue and also extend to regional courts.

Figure 3 Main problems of taking evidence abroad

The legal attorneys also strongly criticize the procedures for collecting evidence abroad, mainly in civil and family matters. The parties are particularly interested in obtaining appropriate evidence towards the implementation of a specific hypothesis. In criminal cases, law enforcement is generally less involved in collecting evidence abroad. It seems that the greatest problems arise when applying to obtain evidence from the testimony of witnesses. Judges, court employees and parties' attorneys strongly believe that interrogating witnesses abroad is complicated, lengthy and ineffective.²⁸

Experts state that international law procedures for questioning witnesses are so complicated that it is not advisable to collect such evidence without direct and explicit necessity. Moreover, advocates and legal advisers emphasize that they are not able to participate in such hearings in person or through a substitute lawyer. As a consequence, the questions asked are not correlated with the evidence assumptions, and their results are sometimes incomprehensible. An additional factor preventing courts from admitting evidence from interrogations abroad is difficulties in serving summons and then forcing people abroad to participate in the witness hearing procedure. Also significant is judges' and court employees' limited competency in ordering hearings for the selection and conduct of an appropriate procedure for examining witnesses abroad. Therefore, parties' attorneys rarely request such actions, and judges are reluctant to order them.²⁹

²⁷ Izabela Haýduk-Hawrylak, Bartłomiej Kolečki, and Anna Wleklińska, *Prawo o ustroju sądów powszechnych: komentarz* (Warszawa: Wydawnictwo C. H. Beck, 2018), 26–36.

²⁸ Wróbel, *Stosowanie prawa Unii Europejskiej przez sądy*, 1:522–36; Martyna Kusak, *Postępowanie karne w sprawach międzynarodowych: podręcznik praktyczny* (Warszawa: Wolters Kluwer Polska, 2017), 116–26, 217–19; Joanna Nowińska, 'Współpraca sądowa w zakresie przeprowadzania dowodów w Unii Europejskiej w świetle Traktatu Lizbońskiego a regulacje polskie', *Teka Komisji Prawniczej*, no. 3 (2010): 168–81.

²⁹ Lorena Bachmaier Winter, 'Transnational Criminal Proceedings, Witness Evidence and Confrontation: Lessons from the ECtHR's Case Law', *Utrecht Law Review* 9 (2013): 127–38; Dorothea Staes, 'The Interrogation of

As a consequence, interrogations of witnesses outside Poland take place very rarely. Judges prefer to admit evidence other than foreign personal evidence. Occasionally, out of necessity or persistence of one of the parties, the court seeks to bring or force witnesses to appear at the hearing in a Polish court building, especially in criminal and family matters. However, if the court agrees to interview witnesses abroad, it most often expects that the interview will be conducted by a Polish consul. Then the witness is summoned for questioning to the Polish consulate directly by the court, much less frequently by the consulate. However, in the common opinion of court employees and lawyers, the questioning of a witness by a consul entails more problems than benefits, as consuls conduct hearings poorly due to errors in the delivery of summons, failure to ask questions sent by the court and parties, inability to conduct interviews with witnesses, and disregarding their professional duties. The reports of the hearings are often not sent to the courts, or they are incorrect or illegible. Additionally, the courts and employees of Polish consulates do not have legal awareness that only Polish citizens can be interviewed in Polish consulates. Hence, such interrogations are often useless and require re-conduct, but in a different form. In addition, the procedures for interrogating witnesses at consulates often provoke disputes between the judiciary and Polish diplomatic services. In the opinion of lawyers, it is incorrect to use consulates.³⁰ Representatives of lawyers from Gdansk and Lublin have noticed this problem as follows:

Once, I participated in a case where the court ordered a hearing of a Polish citizen permanently residing in Spain. As the consul remained passive, did not make any efforts, did not answer, the court had no possibility of punishing such a consul with a fine. After three attempts to apply for a hearing by legal aid, and after eight months of no response, the court decided not to hear witnesses.

I would prefer the questioning of a witness to be carried out by an average judicial authority of another country, or by some prosecutor and functionary authority of that foreign country, rather than by a Polish consul. For the simple reason that it seems to me that a consul is not a person trained to

Witnesses Abroad in Execution of a European Investigation Order: An Examination from Eyes of the Defence' (2011), <https://run.unl.pt/handle/10362/6214>.

³⁰ Marzena Świstak and Natalia Karpiuk, 'Ochrona prawna interesów klienta radcy prawnego w świetle praktyki przeprowadzania przesłuchań przez konsula - wybrana problematyka', *Studia Prawnicze i Administracyjne*, no. 24 (2) (2018): 17–24; Renata Kowalska, 'Czynności konsułów na wnioski organów wymiaru sprawiedliwości - stary model opierający się na potrzebie zmian', *Gdańskie Studia Prawnicze* 2, no. 42 (2019): 251–72; Grzegorz Chmiel, 'Doreczenia Zagraniczne w Postępowaniu Cywilnym i Przeprowadzanie Dowodów Za Granicą. Uwagi Praktyczne', accessed 15 May 2021, <https://www.ora-warszawa.com.pl/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Doreczenia-zagraniczne-w-postepowaniu-cywilnym.pdf>; Piotr Ryłski, 'Przesłuchanie przed konsulem w postępowaniu cywilnym', *Przegląd Sądowy (Warszawa)*, no. 6 (2019): 7–35; 'Konsulowie odmawiają obrońcom udziału w przesłuchaniu? Rzecznik pisze w tej sprawie do Ministra Spraw Zagranicznych', *Rzecznik Praw Obywatelskich*, 9 February 2017, <https://www.rpo.gov.pl/pl/content/konsulowie-odmawiaja-obroncom-udzialu-w-przesluchaniu-rzecznik-pisze-w-tej-sprawie-do-msz>.

ask questions and conduct interrogations. And so, all over the world investigators are competent. Well, maybe in the world of the so-called Western culture.

In the era of judicial cooperation within the European Union, the default form of listening to witnesses is recommending such activities to courts of other countries, or conducting hearings in the form of videoconferences between Polish and foreign courts. Unfortunately, this is used extremely rarely. Plenipotentiaries do not make their application, and courts prefer to use consulates. The main reasons for not using these activities are lack of competency and technical problems. As the jurists point out, most regional courts in Poland do not have the facilities needed to conduct videoconferences, and the tools of district courts are overloaded with videoconferences for the district, or absent. Court employees also do not know how to ask foreign courts to hear witnesses abroad. Another issue is Polish court employees' lack of a foreign language. Therefore, listening to witnesses in these forms occurs even less frequently than through the consul. Unfortunately, Polish lawyers do not try to force the courts to carry out activities in this way.³¹ A Polish legal adviser from Szczecin mentions:

There is a language problem in videoconferencing because the court is not fluent in Croatian. I think those lawyers know English, but I will say yes, it results from a very simple reason: the courts in Poland are lazy. Therefore, it was better to ask the attorneys to make a list of questions, translate this list into English, Croatian or German there, send a request through the ministry to those courts, and let those courts worry about summons, deliveries of correspondence, along with other things, and they will send this protocol. Videoconferencing 'involves many types of procedures'. No court in Poland wants to play such things. It also results from the fact that the courts simply do not want it only and exclusively. Videoconferences have a million technical problems, you will connect or you will not connect; although they have this equipment there, they are not very able to handle it. There are sometimes videoconferences, and of course they are excellent.

All interviewees emphasize that performing any court action abroad greatly lengthens the proceedings. Collecting even trivial evidence abroad extends the case from three to six months when using EU law procedures, or by more than six months with other treaty

³¹ Chmiel, 'Doreczenia Zagraniczne w Postepowaniu Cywilnym i Przeprowadzanie Dowodów Za Granicą. Uwagi Praktyczne'; *Poradnik na temat korzystania z wideokonferencji w postepowaniu transgranicznym* (Luksemburg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2013), <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/30596/qc3012963plc.pdf>; 'Przeprowadzenie Dowodu w Drodze Wideokonferencji', *Europejski Portal E-Sprawiedliwość*, 21 February 2019, https://e-justice.europa.eu/content_taking_evidence_by_videoconferencing-405-pl.do.

procedures. Therefore, lawyers, judges and court employees try not to use cross-border evidence procedures, except when absolutely necessary.

The number of court problems related to the execution of procedures containing foreign elements is large. Polish lawyers notice only some of them, both the most acute problems and minor ones. Lawyers specializing in family law emphasize that courts have problems with enforcing their own decisions and judgments of foreign courts regarding child support, caring for a child, making decisions in important matters of a child, changing the amount of child support, and deprivation of child custody. In the cross-border perspective, this is related to the court staff's lack of understanding and competence in applying appropriate procedures. Polish and foreign court employees also lack skills in communicating with foreign courts and services. Plenipotentiaries note that Polish courts are unable to understand the different legal systems of different countries; this usually manifests itself in a lack of cooperation with foreign institutions related to childcare (family probation officers, child welfare services, social welfare). It must be admitted, however, that employees of Polish courts are heavily burdened with minor enforcement cases in family matters, which makes the operation of domestic courts in international family matters ineffective and complicated.³² This is well presented by an attorney from Bydgoszcz:

In these international cases, these issues – related to, for example, the enforcement of child support decisions – work very poorly. There are too many obligations imposed on a Polish citizen, who has to arrange a lot of things to get the case to the appropriate court. Because it depends who is carrying out this execution. In some countries there are courts, in others there are bailiffs, etc. It seems to me that this should be at the level of the Ministries of Justice, because what can such a Pole do, even if he has a lawyer. We also do not have such possibilities to determine where he works, where he lives, because it is necessary to send these documents according to the properties of the place of residence.

The last problem of the Polish justice system in the field of foreign affairs is cooperation with translators and other specialists in Oz and Kop cases. Polish jurists emphasize

³² 'Sprawy Rodzinne', *Europejski Portal E-Sprawiedliwość*, 2 June 2020, https://e-justice.europa.eu/content_family_matters-44-pl.do; Wojciech Maciejko, Marta Romańska, and Małgorzata Karcz, *Alimenty: komentarz*, ed. Jacek Ignaczewski (Warszawa: Wydawnictwo C.H. Beck, 2016), 493–587, 621–55; 'Alimenty Od Rodzica Przebywającego Za Granicą', *Powroty.Gov.Pl*, 23 February 2021, <https://powroty.gov.pl/alimenty-od-rodzica-przebywajacego-za-granica-10172>; Agata Chelstowska, *Alimenty Na Dzieci - Diagnoza Polskiego Systemu i Przegląd Praktyk Zagranicznych* (Warszawa: Instytut Spraw Publicznych, 2016), 27–54, <https://www.rpo.gov.pl/sites/default/files/Agata%20Che%20C5%82stowska%20Alimenty%20-%20diagnoza.%20Raport%20ISP.pdf>; Justyna Ostafil, 'Dochodzenie alimentów za granicą na podstawie Konwencji nowojorskiej z 1956 r. i Konwencji haskiej z 2007 r.' (praca magisterska, Uniwersytet Jagielloński, 2020), <https://ruj.uj.edu.pl/xmlui/handle/item/241978>.

that most applications submitted by courts abroad require translation. In Poland, the number of translators is so small that in the case of languages other than English, German and Russian, the translation time extends the procedure by at least several months. It also happens that the translations are defective, which causes technical but very troublesome problems.³³ Polish lawyers also indicate that the courts are not willing to use the services of experts in the field of the law of other countries; this often results in a judge's incorrect assessment of the legal status applicable abroad.³⁴ These problems are critically assessed, among others, by lawyers from Bydgoszcz:

It depends on what language is translated. Because when it comes to translators from German, English, Russian, there is no problem. And when it comes to Italian, French, it takes a little longer. Recently, a colleague had a problem: he was looking for a Dutch interpreter, so the court had to ask ... not the court, a colleague had to ask Lublin for a translation, and he asked the court to extend the deadline because he could not perform it. That would be a problem, and he actually waited longer there; but when it comes to translations into English, German, Russian, depending on the size of the document, but if it is half a page of the certificate, we have a translation overnight.

Legal specialists also note other problems of the Polish judiciary when dealing with foreign elements in court proceedings. It is worth noting that, in their opinion, the handling of non-national elements in criminal cases is conducted quite correctly. However, other types of cases suffer from an increasing number of inconveniences and errors. Unfortunately, lawyers emphasize that the number of problems is not decreasing, it is even increasing. Along with the migration of Poles and Poland's integration with the European Union, the number of foreign elements in the courts is growing rapidly, and is becoming ever more complicated. Courts are not prepared for them, and jurists are very critical and pessimistic about the future. They stress that without structural changes, the problems of handling foreign affairs will worsen. Many of them propose appointing specialized units for foreign affairs in courts, and to train judges and

³³ Paweł Ostaszewski and Justyna Włodarczyk-Madejska, *Tłumaczenia Poświadczone w Praktyce Wymiaru Sprawiedliwości* (Warszawa: Instytut Wymiaru Sprawiedliwości, 2016), 2–44, https://iws.gov.pl/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/IWS_Ostaszewski-P.-W%C5%82odarczyk-Madejska-J._T%C5%82umaczenia-po%C5%9Bwiadczone.pdf; Karolina Nartowska, 'Tłumaczenie sądowe w Polsce. Analiza rynku', *Lingua Legis*, no. 20 (December 2011): 22–29.

³⁴ Michał Wojewoda, 'Stwierdzenie treści właściwego prawa obcego przez sędziego krajowego (sędziego sądu rodzinnego)' (Łódź), accessed 15 May 2021, <http://www.ssrwp.pl/pliki/wojewoda-14-1.pdf>; Marta Knotz, 'Praktyczne Informacje Dotyczące Ustalania Tekstu Prawa Obcego', *Forum Współpracy Sędziów*, 4 July 2020, <https://forumfws.eu/obrot-zagraniczny/ustalanie-tekstu-prawa-obcego/>; Paweł Banul, 'Opinia Biegłego Co Do Prawa Obcego w Polskim Postępowaniu Cywilnym', *Polski Proces Cywilny*, no. 3 (2019): 346–63, <https://sip.lex.pl/#/publication/151355057>.

employees in this area. There are also opinions that, following the French example, specialized courts should be established for handling international cases in Poland.³⁵

Conclusions

The number and importance of court cases with foreign elements is increasing in Polish courts every year. However, the courts are unable to handle new foreign elements, as is noticed by the beneficiaries of the courts and the parties' attorneys. They repeatedly emphasize that the courts have enormous problems in using the institutions of international law during the judgement process. Judges do not know the rules of using the acts of international law, especially the European Union. They often confuse procedures and are unable to apply them, do not ask for help from international tribunals, or simply do not follow them. Lawyers emphasize that this can happen for such mundane reasons as exhaustion or laziness. It seems that Polish judges, despite the passage of several years, practically are not integrated with the structures of the European Union; they are European courts only in theory. Consequently, in judicial practice, the effective use of the institutions of international law is still illusory and highly ineffective.

In Polish courts, international auxiliary activities significantly support the trial process. Polish law practitioners emphasize that in many situations they are even more important than issuing judgments. These procedures are very complicated and require great competence in their application; but employees are still unable to properly deliver correspondence abroad, to collect evidence abroad, or to cooperate with translators, experts, institutions and foreign courts. As a result, most cases with foreign elements are very lengthy, and many procedures in this area remain only theoretical or are extremely rarely used.

Problems in judging cases with foreign elements and international auxiliary activities mean that the Polish judiciary deals such cases highly ineffectively. Indeed, attorneys advise against bringing such cases to court. Many of them postulate that, if possible, cases should be brought to courts of other countries. Polish jurists do not expect that their clients' cases, which involve international issues, will ever be settled in Polish courts. Despite the activity of about 20 judges and other specialists in the field of international court cases, the state of proceedings with foreign elements in Polish courts is highly unsatisfactory, with no indication that it will improve soon.

³⁵ Olga Bobrzyńska, *Wyspecjalizowany sąd do międzynarodowych spraw handlowych – rozwiązanie francuskie z 2018 r.* (Warszawa: Instytut Wymiaru Sprawiedliwości, 2019), 5–28, https://iws.gov.pl/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/IWS_Bobrzy%C5%84ska-O._Wyspecjalizowany-s%C4%85d-domi%C4%99dzynar.-spraw-handlowych-rozwi%C4%85zanie-francuskie-z-2018-r.pdf.

In this situation, domestic lawyers call for urgent, fundamental remedial procedures against the chaos in the field of judicial service of international cases. Without these changes, the handling of international affairs will cease completely, and cases with foreign elements will be marginalized, suspended and discontinued. The conclusions that can be drawn from conversations with Polish lawyers and other analyses show that the most urgent remedial steps to be taken include:

1. Introduction to the initial education of judges, assessors, assistant judges and court referendaries on a greater number of international topics, mainly EU law;
2. Introducing compulsory internships, apprenticeships and job shadowing for judges and other court employees in foreign courts;
3. Conducting regular training courses for judges and mainly court employees in the field of foreign relations;
4. Conducting regular language training for all court employees;
5. Creation of a nationwide information point on international matters in the Ministry of Justice, and its integration with coordinators for international cooperation in district courts, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and bar associations;
6. Creating a uniform publication or website with clear, practical charts, diagrams, advice and templates of international proceedings, for both judges and court employees;
7. Revise all national acts and international agreements relating to the performance of ancillary judicial activities (evidence, service) and, if necessary, conclude a single, multilateral international agreement in these areas or comply with EU rules;
8. Technical and organizational improvement of work and communication with consulates, creating more rooms for videoconferencing, employing more support staff and providing them with technical resources (e.g. premises);
9. Introducing default electronic deliveries in foreign relations;
10. Integration of Polish judges and court employees with their counterparts abroad;
11. Increasing remuneration for court employees specialized in international cases.

The introduction of these solutions cannot guarantee that all courts' international problems will be resolved. However, their implementation should lead to the improvement of these procedures. Long-term court practice in international matters seems to be a particularly effective solution. Only after many years of intensive dealing with foreign affairs may the situation change; and the external activity of the European Union institutions plays an important role here. Currently, political processes in Poland delay and hinder the proper implementation of international procedures in Polish courts. Without improving their day-to-day service, the

Polish judiciary will regress and become alienated from European and global solutions. Therefore, the introduction of reforms postulated by the legal community, and deepened integration of the Polish judicial system with the systems of other EU countries, seem to be essential. Only then will the courts' specific problems in handling foreign elements eventually cease.

- 'Alimenty Od Rodzica Przebywającego Za Granicą'. *Powroty.Gov.Pl*, 23 February 2021. <https://powroty.gov.pl/alimenty-od-rodzica-przebywajacego-za-granica-10172>.
- 'Aplikacja sędziowska'. *Krajowa Szkoła Sądownictwa i Prokuratury*. Accessed 15 May 2021. [/aplikacje/programy-aplikacji/aplikacja-sedziowska](#).
- 'ATLAS.ti'. *ATLAS.ti*, 2021. <https://atlasti.com/>.
- Babbie, Earl R. *Podstawy Badań Społecznych*. Translated by Witold Betkiewicz. Warszawa: Wydawnictwo Naukowe PWN, 2008.
- Banul, Paweł. 'Opinia Bieglego Co Do Prawa Obcego w Polskim Postępowaniu Cywilnym'. *Polski Proces Cywilny*, no. 3 (2019). <https://sip.lex.pl/#/publication/151355057>.
- Barcik, Jacek. 'Pytania Prejudycjalne Polskich Sądów'. *Iustitia*, no. 3 (2013): 1–4.
- Berelson, Bernard. *Content Analysis in Communication Research*. New York: Hafner, 1971.
- Bobrzyńska, Olga. *Wyspecjalizowany sąd do międzynarodowych spraw handlowych – rozwiązanie francuskie z 2018 r.* Warszawa: Instytut Wymiaru Sprawiedliwości, 2019. https://iws.gov.pl/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/IWS_Bobrzy%C5%84ska-O._Wyspecjalizowany-s%C4%85d-do-mi%C4%99dzynar.-spraw-handlowych-rozwi%C4%85zanie-francuskie-z-2018-r.pdf.
- Borowska, Katarzyna. 'Coraz więcej kobiet jest adwokatami'. *Rzeczpospolita*, no. 01.08.2012. Accessed 12 May 2021. <https://www.rp.pl/artukul/920818-Coraz-wiecej-kobiet-jest-adwokatami.html>.
- Buczma, Sławomir R, and Józef Gemra. *Metodyka pracy w sprawach karnych ze stosunków międzynarodowych*. Warszawa; Kraków: Wydawnictwo C. H. Beck ; Krajowa Szkoła Sądownictwa i Prokuratury, 2013. <https://www.kSSIP.gov.pl/kSSIP/sites/default/files/068fb43699bf48acc340057c76333f16.pdf>.
- Chełstowska, Agata. *Alimenty Na Dzieci - Diagnoza Polskiego Systemu i Przegląd Praktyk Zagranicznych*. Warszawa: Instytut Spraw Publicznych, 2016. <https://www.rpo.gov.pl/sites/default/files/Agata%20Che%C5%82stowska%20Alimenty%20-%20diagnoza.%20Raport%20ISP.pdf>.
- Chmiel, Grzegorz. 'Doreczenia Zagraniczne w Postępowaniu Cywilnym i Przeprowadzanie Dowodów Za Granicą. Uwagi Praktyczne'. Accessed 15 May 2021. <https://www.ora-warszawa.com.pl/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Doreczenia-zagraniczne-w-postepowaniu-cywilnym.pdf>.
- . 'Obrót zagraniczny w praktyce'. 10 May 2021. <https://forumfws.eu/obr%C3%B3t-zagraniczny-materia%C5%82y-szkoleniowe-g.-chmiel.pdf>.
- Cholewa, Joanna. 'Jak język polski i francuski odzwierciedla wzajemne postrzeganie Polaków i Francuzów?' In *Anglosasi, Francuzi i Polacy: wzajemny wizerunek dawniej i dziś*, edited by Piotr Guzowski and Małgorzata Kamecka, 313–23. Białystok: Wydawnictwo Uniwersytetu w Białymstoku, 2005. https://repozytorium.uwb.edu.pl/jspui/bitstream/11320/4650/1/Joanna_Cholewa_Jak_jezyk_polski_i_francuski_odzwierciedla_wzajemne_postrzeganie_Polakow_i_Francuzow.pdf.

- Cichomska, Marta. 'Wybór prawa w postępowaniu cywilnym'. Rozprawa doktorska, Uniwersytet Warszawski, 2015. <https://depotuw.ceon.pl/handle/item/1212>.
- Ciszewski, Jan. *Obrót prawny z zagranicą w sprawach cywilnych i karnych*. Warszawa: Wolters Kluwer, 2017.
- 'Court of Justice of the European Union'. Accessed 15 May 2021. https://curia.europa.eu/jcms/jcms/j_6/en/.
- Czekala, Bartosz, and Bogusław Kromołowski. 'Pytania prejudycjalne do Trybunału Sprawiedliwości Unii Europejskiej w polskim postępowaniu karnym'. *Gubernaculum et Administratio* 2015, no. 1 (11) (2015): 11–27.
- Daniel, Krystyna. 'Kryzys społecznego zaufania do sądów'. *Studia Socjologiczne* 2 (185) (2007): 61–82.
- 'Doręczenia Pism Sądowych w Postępowaniu Cywilnym w Obrocie Krajowym'. Rozprawa doktorska, Uniwersytet im. Adama Mickiewicza w Poznaniu, 2012. https://repozytorium.amu.edu.pl/bitstream/10593/5797/1/Daria_Dasewicz-Buchowska.pdf.
- 'European Court of Human Rights'. Accessed 16 January 2021. <https://www.echr.coe.int/Pages/home.aspx?p=home>.
- 'European Judicial Network (EJN)'. Accessed 1 November 2020. https://www.ejn-crimjust.europa.eu/ejn/EJN_Home.aspx.
- 'Forum Współpracy Sędziów'. FWS. Accessed 15 May 2021. <https://forumfws.eu/inicjatywy-lokalne/sedziowie-lodzcy/>.
- Frankfort-Nachmias, Chava, and David Nachmias. *Metody Badawcze w Naukach Społecznych*. Poznań: Zysk i S-ka, 2001.
- Gołaczyński, Jacek, Wojciech Popiołek, Katarzyna Bagan-Kurluta, Katarzyna Anna Dadańska, Kinga Flaga-Gieruszyńska, Bogusława Gnela, Anna Juryk, et al. *Kolizyjne i procesowe aspekty prawa rodzinnego*. Warszawa: Wydawnictwo C H. Beck, 2019.
- Haýduk-Hawrylak, Izabela, Bartłomiej Kołdecki, and Anna Wlekińska. *Prawo o ustroju sądów powszechnych: komentarz*. Warszawa: Wydawnictwo C. H. Beck, 2018.
- Horton, Joanne, Richard Macve, and Geert Struyven. 'Qualitative Research: Experiences in Using Semi-Structured Interviews'. In *The Real Life Guide to Accounting Research*, edited by Christopher Humphrey and Bill Lee, 339–57. Oxford: Elsevier, 2004. doi:10.1016/B978-008043972-3/50022-0.
- Joński, Kamil. *Efektywność sądownictwa powszechnego - podstawowe problemy*. Warszawa: Instytut Wymiaru Sprawiedliwości, 2016. https://iws.gov.pl/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/IWS_Jo%C5%84ski-K._Efektywno%C5%9B%C4%87-s%C4%85downictwa-powszechnego1.pdf.
- Kędziński, Dawid. 'Metodologia i Paradygmat Polskich Szczegółowych Nauk Prawnych'. *Transformacje Prawa Prywatnego*, no. 3 (29 September 2018): 5–58.
- Kloc, Katarzyna. 'Język obcy a praca w zawodzie prawnika'. *Goldenline.pl*, 2020. https://www.goldenline.pl/grupy/Przedsiębiorcy_biznesmeni/prawo/jezyk-obcy-a-praca-w-zawodzie-prawnika,1770622/.
- Knotz, Marta. 'Praktyczne Informacje Dotyczące Ustalania Tekstu Prawa Obcego'. *Forum Współpracy Sędziów*, 4 July 2020. <https://forumfws.eu/obrot-zagraniczny/ustalanie-tekstu-prawa-obcego/>.
- Kociołowicz-Wisniewska, Bogna, and Bartosz Pilitowski. *Ocena polskiego sądownictwa w świetle badań*. Warszawa: Fundacja Court Watch Polska, 2017. <https://courtwatch.pl/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/Raport-Fundacji-Court-Watch-Polska-Ocena-polskich-s%C4%85d%C3%B3w-w-%C5%9Bwietle-bada%C5%84-maj-2017.pdf>.

- ‘Konsulowie odmawiają obrońcom udziału w przesłuchaniu? Rzecznik pisze w tej sprawie do Ministra Spraw Zagranicznych’. *Rzecznik Praw Obywatelskich*, 9 February 2017. <https://www.rpo.gov.pl/pl/content/konsulowie-odmawiaja-obroncom-udzialu-w-przesluchaniu-rzecznik-pisze-w-tej-sprawie-do-msz>.
- Kowalska, Renata. ‘Czynności konsułów na wniosek organów wymiaru sprawiedliwości - stary model opierający się na potrzebie zmian’. *Gdańskie Studia Prawnicze* 2, no. 42 (2019): 251–72.
- ‘Krajowa Izba Radców Prawnych’. *Krajowa Izba Radców Prawnych*, 2021. <http://kirp.pl>.
- Kusak, Martyna. *Postępowanie karne w sprawach międzynarodowych: podręcznik praktyczny*. Warszawa: Wolters Kluwer Polska, 2017.
- Kvale, Steinar. *Prowadzenie wywiadów*. Translated by Agata Dziuban. Niezbędnik Badacza. Warszawa: Wydawnictwo Naukowe PWN, 2012. <http://emp0pwn0storage0prod.blob.core.windows.net/kipwnaddons/65438.pdf>.
- Lewicka, Renata. ‘Doręczenia zagraniczne w postępowaniu administracyjnym i sądowniczym – problemy praktyczne’. *Acta Universitatis Lodzensis. Folia Iuridica*, no. 77 (2016): 155–70. doi:10.18778/0208-6069.77.12.
- Lipiec, Stanisław. ‘Świadczenie Międzynarodowych Usług Prawniczych. Studium Socjologiczno-Prawne Polskich Prawników, Rozprawa Doktorska’, 2020.
- Maciejko, Wojciech, Marta Romańska, and Małgorzata Karcz. *Alimenty: komentarz*. Edited by Jacek Ignaczewski. Warszawa: Wydawnictwo C.H. Beck, 2016.
- McIntosh, Michele J., and Janice M. Morse. ‘Situating and Constructing Diversity in Semi-Structured Interviews’. *Global Qualitative Nursing Research*, no. 2 (1 January 2015): 1–12. doi:10.1177/2333393615597674.
- McIntyre, Joe. ‘Introduction to the Judicial Function’. In *The Judicial Function: Fundamental Principles of Contemporary Judging*, edited by Joe McIntyre, 23–31. Singapore: Springer, 2019. doi:10.1007/978-981-32-9115-7_2.
- . ‘The Development of Principles of Contemporary Judging’. In *The Judicial Function: Fundamental Principles of Contemporary Judging*, edited by Joe McIntyre, 3–19. Singapore: Springer, 2019. doi:10.1007/978-981-32-9115-7_1.
- Michalski, Bartosz. ‘Pracownicy sądów doszli do ściany. Urzędnicy i asystenci odchodzą, nowych nie widać’. *Dziennik. Gazeta Prawna*, 15 May 2019. <https://prawo.gazetaprawna.pl/artykuly/1411938,protest-oczami-pracownikow-sadownictwa.html>.
- Moreno-Lax, Violeta, and Paul Gragl. ‘Introduction: Beyond Monism, Dualism, Pluralism: The Quest for a (Fully-Fledged) Theoretical Framework: Co-Implication, Embeddedness, and Interdependency between Public International Law and EU Law’. *Yearbook of European Law* 35, no. 1 (1 December 2016): 455–70. doi:10.1093/yel/yew016.
- ‘Naczelna Rada Adwokacka’, 2021. <http://www.nra.pl>.
- Nartowska, Karolina. ‘Tłumaczenie sądowe w Polsce. Analiza rynku’. *Lingua Legis*, no. 20 (December 2011): 22–29.
- ‘Nasze Szkolenia Ustawiczne’. *Krajowa Szkoła Sądownictwa i Prokuratury*. Accessed 15 May 2021. https://ekSSIP.kSSIP.gov.pl/local/guest_pages/our-courses.php.
- Nicpoń, Małgorzata, and Radosław Marzęcki. ‘Pogłębiony wywiad indywidualny w badaniach politologicznych’. In *Przeszłość, teraźniejszość, przyszłość: problemy badawcze młodych politologów*, 245–52. Kraków: Libron, 2010. <http://przemek.wammoda.com/polis/ksmp/book/IIKSMPmarzecki.pdf>.
- Nowińska, Joanna. ‘Współpraca sądowa w zakresie przeprowadzania dowodów w Unii Europejskiej w świetle Traktatu Lizbońskiego a regulacje polskie’. *Teka Komisji Prawniczej*, no. 3 (2010): 164–81.

- Ostafil, Justyna. 'Dochodzenie alimentów za granicą na podstawie Konwencji nowojorskiej z 1956 r. i Konwencji haskiej z 2007 r.' Praca magisterska, Uniwersytet Jagielloński, 2020. <https://ruj.uj.edu.pl/xmlui/handle/item/241978>.
- Ostaszewski, Paweł, and Justyna Włodarczyk-Madejska. *Tłumaczenia Poświadczone w Praktyce Wymiaru Sprawiedliwości*. Warszawa: Instytut Wymiaru Sprawiedliwości, 2016. https://iws.gov.pl/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/IWS_Ostaszewski-P.-W%C5%82odarczyk-Madejska-J._T%C5%82umaczenia-po%C5%9Bwiadczone.pdf.
- Pisarek, Walery. *Analiza Zawartości Prasy*. Kraków: Ośrodek Badań Prasoznawczych, 1983.
- Poradnik na temat korzystania z wideokonferencji w postępowaniu transgranicznym*. Luksemburg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2013. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/30596/qc3012963plc.pdf>.
- 'Przeprowadzenie Dowodu w Drodze Wideokonferencji'. *Europejski Portal E-Sprawiedliwość*, 21 February 2019. https://e-justice.europa.eu/content_taking_evidence_by_videoconferencing-405-pl.do.
- Przybyłowska, Ilona. 'Wywiad swobodny ze standaryzowaną listą poszukiwanych informacji i możliwości jego zastosowania w badaniach socjologicznych'. *Przegląd Socjologiczny*, no. 30 (1978): 62–63.
- Qu, Sandy Q, and John Dumay. 'The Qualitative Research Interview'. *Qualitative Research in Accounting & Management* 8, no. 3 (2011): 238–64.
- Rozporządzenie Ministra Sprawiedliwości z dnia 28 stycznia 2002 r. w sprawie szczegółowych czynności sądów w sprawach z zakresu międzynarodowego postępowania cywilnego oraz karnego w stosunkach międzynarodowych, Pub. L. No. Dz. U. z 2014 r. poz. 1657 z późn. zm.) (n.d.).
- Rylski, Piotr. 'Przesłuchanie przed konsulem w postępowaniu cywilnym'. *Przegląd Sądowy (Warszawa)*, no. 6 (2019): 7–35.
- . 'Skuteczność doręczeń w procesie cywilnym'. *Prawo w Działaniu. Sprawy Cywilne*, no. 15 (2013): 31.
- Rymar, Stanisław. 'Świadczenie stałej pomocy prawnej w Polsce przez zagranicznych prawników'. *Palestra*, no. 7–8 (2002): 7–11.
- 'Sąd Okręgowy w Warszawie'. Accessed 15 May 2021. <https://bip.warszawa.so.gov.pl/>.
- 'Sąd Rejonowy Dla m.St. Warszawy w Warszawie'. Accessed 15 May 2021. <http://warszawa.sr.gov.pl/>.
- Sadomski, Jacek. 'Pytania prejudycjalne polskich sądów powszechnych'. *Prawo w Działaniu*, no. 20 (2014): 26–93.
- Skibicki, Rafał. 'Międzynarodowe Postępowanie Cywilne'. Wrocław, 10 February 2021. <https://prawo.uni.wroc.pl/sites/default/files/students-resources/Zaj%C4%99cia%20nr%2010%20-%20MPC.pdf>.
- 'SkryBot'. *Skrybot*, 2021. <https://skrybot.pl>.
- 'Sprawy Rodzinne'. *Europejski Portal E-Sprawiedliwość*, 2 June 2020. https://e-justice.europa.eu/content_family_matters-44-pl.do.
- Staes, Dorothea. 'The Interrogation of Witnesses Abroad in Execution of a European Investigation Order: An Examination from Eyes of the Defence'. 2011. <https://run.unl.pt/handle/10362/6214>.
- Stypułkowska, Maria. 'Trudna droga kobiet do wykonywania zawodów prawniczych'. *Palestra* 38, no. 9–10 (1994): 139–49.
- Świstak, Marzena, and Natalia Karpiuk. 'Ochrona prawna interesów klienta radcy prawnego w świetle praktyki przeprowadzania przesłuchań przez konsula - wybrana problematyka'. *Studia Prawnicze i Administracyjne*, no. 24 (2) (2018): 17–24.
- Szpunar, Maciej. 'Wybrane problemy stosowania prawa Unii Europejskiej przed sądami państw członkowskich'. *Palestra*, no. 5 (2020).

- <https://palestra.pl/pl/czasopismo/wydanie/5-2020/artykul/wybrane-problemy-stosowania-prawa-unii-europejskiej-przed-sadami-panstw-czlonkowskich>.
- Ustawa z dnia 27 lipca 2001 r. Prawo o ustroju sądów powszechnych, Pub. L. No. Dz. U. z 2020 r. poz. 2072 (n.d.).
- Winter, Lorena Bachmaier. 'Transnational Criminal Proceedings, Witness Evidence and Confrontation: Lessons from the ECtHR's Case Law'. *Utrecht Law Review* 9 (2013): 127.
- Wojewoda, Michał. 'Stwierdzenie treści właściwego prawa obcego przez sędziego krajowego (sędziego sądu rodzinnego)'. Łódź. Accessed 15 May 2021. <http://www.ssrwp.pl/pliki/wojewoda-14-1.pdf>.
- Wróbel, Andrzej, ed. *Stosowanie prawa Unii Europejskiej przez sądy*. Vol. 1. Warszawa: Wolters Kluwer, 2010.
- Wysmułek, Ilona, and Olena Oleksiyenko. *Strukturalne zróżnicowanie znajomości języków obcych: wybrane wyniki Polskiego Badania Panelowego POLPAN 1988-2013*. Warszawa: Zespół Porównawczych Analiz Nierówności Społecznych, Instytut Filozofii i Socjologii Polskiej Akademii Nauk, 2015. http://polpan.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/05/POLPAN_raport_Znajomosc-jezykow.pdf.
- Zarządzenie Ministra Sprawiedliwości z dnia 19 czerwca 2019 r. w sprawie organizacji i zakresu działania sekretariatów sądowych oraz innych działów administracji sądowej, Pub. L. No. Dz. U. M. S. z 2019 r, poz. 138 (2019). <https://www.infor.pl/akt-prawny/U06.2019.043.0000138,zarzadzenie-ministra-sprawiedliwosci-w-sprawie-organizacji-i-zakresu-dzialania-sekretariatow-sadowych-oraz-innych-dzialow-administracji-sadowej.html>.
- Ziegler, Katja S. 'The Relationship between EU Law and International Law'. SSRN Scholarly Paper. Rochester, NY: Social Science Research Network, 22 January 2015. <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=2554069>.